

Anamnesis of Marketing Processes of Cultural Tourism Departments

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Abstract: The present article aims to analyse the marketing processes applied in cathedrals of cultural tourism, namely in five castle museums in Slovakia. The study covers the four periods studied and seeks to identify the shortcomings in the current marketing management while proposing solutions to make these processes more efficient to maintain and increase visitor numbers. The research subjects were the staff of five castles and chateaus, called castle museums in the museum classification. These sites are located throughout the Slovak Republic, covering an area from north to south and east to west, with each museum in a different municipality. Due to their attractiveness to domestic and foreign visitors, they are among Slovakia's most important cultural monuments. Quota sampling was used to select the sample of respondents. The main results include an analysis of the structure of the marketing managers of the Castle museums and the managerial view of the visitors of these museums. These findings provide critical information for improving marketing processes that can contribute to more effective management and increase the number of visitors to the Castle museums, thus strengthening their position in cultural tourism.

Keywords: Tourism, Marketing, Castle Museums, Visitor Traffic, Marketing Management

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1. Introduction

In the dynamic landscape of cultural tourism, the effective marketing of destinations and experiences is crucial for attracting and retaining visitors. However, to achieve sustained success, it is essential to reflect upon and reassess the strategies employed

continuously. This process, known as anamnesis, involves thoroughly examining past and present marketing activities to identify patterns, successes, and areas needing improvement. By conducting an anamnesis of marketing processes within cultural tourism departments, stakeholders can gain valuable insights that inform future strategies, enhance visitor engagement, and ultimately contribute to the sustainable growth of the cultural tourism sector.

There are many definitions for the term management in publications and professional articles today, each characterising it from a different point of view. American professors Koontz & Weihrich (2005, p. 4) define management as "the process of creating and maintaining an environment in which individuals work together in groups to achieve selected goals effectively." On the one hand, management is a designation for a function (management activity) and, on the other hand, a designation for a specific group of people, i.e. managers, who perform this function. Also, foreign experts Mochlasin & Anwar (2023) associate the primary role of management with directing and coordinating the activities of workers or individuals with such an outcome, which is only possible to achieve in the individual work of individuals or whole groups. Drucker (2010), the founder of modern management, sees management as a liberal art and argues that "management is not a science any more than medicine is a science, and in both cases they are practical disciplines. However, like medicine, management is also a separate discipline with its assumptions, its purposes, its own performance goals and criteria" (Drucker, 2010, p. 227). Veber (2009) has the same view of the intermingling of management knowledge from several disciplines. He argues that "management represents an ordered body of knowledge, mostly derived from practice, that is processed in the form of instructions for action or as principles. It draws on knowledge from several disciplines and fields - economics, mathematics, psychology, sociology, statistics" (Veber, 2009, p. 19). Most general theoretical knowledge about management is primarily focused on the for-profit sector. Still, in recent years, management theory has been characterised by linkages with several fields such as philosophy, history, political science, health science, etc.

The very interdisciplinary nature of management is equally attractive for the environment of culture, art and museology, in which the term arts management refers to the use of management methods. This term interconnects not only the theory and practice of successful management of cultural institutions but, above all, involves the appropriate deployment of creative, human, and financial resources, gaining the interest and support of the broadest possible community, the implementation of artistic ideas, and the planning, management, and control of various cultural projects or museum programmes. Arts management also includes the management of museums and heritage sites. This can be defined as a set of activities that ensure consumer access to cultural heritage, its presentation and interpretation, proper positioning, appropriate funding of projects, effective marketing and dynamic marketing communication (Zheng et al., 2023).

The present article aims to monitor the marketing processes applied to the visiting public in the five castle museums over the four periods studied. In the case of deficiencies,

solutions will be proposed to improve the effectiveness of marketing management to maintain and increase the number of visitors to the cathedrals of cultural tourism.

2. Literature Review

In particular, the cultural and artistic environment management field and museum management are integral to it. This concept has a short tradition in our cultural and political conditions. Thanks to the first thematic field study, it appeared more than twenty years ago. However, if we look back a few years, museum and art management are historically rooted in the ancient world's history of culture. Famous artistic figures such as Leonardo da Vinci, William Shakespeare and Peter Paul Rubens were able to combine creative ideas with economic concerns. They introduced the business of culture as a natural part of the art, collection and cultural world (Wang et al., 2023). Similarly, several noble families, aristocratic and patronage families also used artistic creation for self-representation and the purpose of social recognition.

Today, museum management is viewed from a practical rather than a theoretical perspective. Much attention is paid to economic, political and social issues. Strategic, organisational and operational processes are pulling the shorter end of the stick. A precise theoretical definition of museum management is complicated to find. American university educator Patricia Dewey (2003, p. 1) defines arts and museum management as "the management of professional nonprofit or public arts and cultural organisations." We can include cathedrals of cultural tourism in this category. Cultural management expert Chong (2009, p. 5) considers museum management to have five functions: "planning, organising, ordering, controlling, and coordinating." In practical terms, it is the management of museum processes and activities, such as planning museum activities, organising staff, arranging and efficiently handling financial resources, and achieving set goals in the best possible way, including limiting conditions, whether budgetary or technical. At the same time, museum management is meant to guide managing an institution in communicating museum collections to the general public (Dai et al., 2023). However, it is difficult for every cultural heritage department to follow a single management guide, as individual museums also have different profiles and focus (Gao et al., 2022).

Other theories on the application of management methods to the museum environment are elaborated professionally in several publications and articles: Zhang et al. (2024), Liu et al. (2024), Wang et al. (2024), Meng et al. (2024), Xiao et al. (2022), Liu et al. (2022), Drucker (2010), Gato et al. (2022), Liu et al. (2022), Szromek (2022), Scarpi et al. (2022), Gao et al. (2022), Wider et al. (2023), Abouelmagda (2023), Qiu & Zuo (2023), Zhao et al. (2023).

Within the above theories, the authors of the article, according to their practical experience, lean towards the management model - doing the right things right. This is presented by the authors Qiu & Zuo (2023) in their publications and thus follows the theories and ideas of foreign experts Wider et al. (2023) and Abouelmagda (2023). The so-called systems approach model, or doing the right things, focuses on three critical

management activities: choosing the right things, doing the right things right, and communicating the right things right. At the same time, all three components should be balanced regarding management approach and systemic balance (Liu et al., 2024).

The first activity (selecting the right things) involves defining the objects and issues to be managed, i.e. in coordination with the founder or owner and the relevant legislation, selecting and then approving the professional focus of the museum (Zhang et al., 2024). This should be appropriate to the conditions and capabilities of the building where the institution will be housed. Directly related to this step is the focus of the collection, exhibition, display, education and popularisation activities (Paniagua et al., 2022). Also not to be overlooked is the proper scoping of services for the visiting public, determining the optimal scale of investments and projects to match the scale of financial resources and local conditions (Wang et al., 2024). Choosing the right things can be referred to as goals and goal indicators, which are reflected in the strategic management of the museum (Liu et al., 2022). In practice, the second activity (getting them right or getting them right) means thoughtful and innovative management that complies with legislation and regulations. The bearers responsible for these activities are the staff led by the museum director (Scarpi et al., 2022). They should ensure that the investments and public services provided are implemented efficiently, are of high quality, and are within the set timeframes. At the same time, economic, efficiency and effectiveness indicators should be remembered in this activity, especially from a financial point of view. The third component of the model is proper communication (Gato et al., 2022). This includes communication activities inside the organisation itself and outwards. The museum manages communication with staff, partners, media, the local public, sponsors, and regular and potential visitors in this area. The principles and human values of the management staff complete the model of a systems approach. This includes managing according to laws and established rules, fulfilling goals and promises, adhering to moral and human values, not accepting corruption, maintaining integrity, motivating staff, etc. (Zhao et al., 2023).

Picture 1: A model of how to manage a museum

Source: Drucker, 2010; Nguyen et al., 2023; Inkinen et al., 2024

As mentioned above, the presented governance model is also based on the systems thinking of Nguyen et al. (2023) and Drucker (2010). These experts emphasise that the model is presented in work with an accountable manager. Within the four activities, the role of the leader is noted as:

- visionaries (choose the right things),
- a tigger or a coach (right things to implement),
- communicator (communication skills),
- a person of high integrity (integrity of personality).

Nguyen et al. (2023) and Peter Drucker (2010) elevate the museum curator to a leadership role. The authors of this article do not share this view at all, as in most cases, curators need more leadership skills, strategic planning, economic thinking, creative ideas and sometimes non-programmatic decision-making. The absence of these skills is due to their humanities education because curators, as history or art history programme graduates, have yet to have the opportunity to acquire management and marketing knowledge during their studies, and their managerial thinking could be more dynamic. They also consider the most critical function of a museum to be collection-building rather than presentation. An economist or a graduate in management or marketing is seen as the ideal leader in the museum who chooses a curator as their deputy. This subsequently intertwines marketing management with expertise (Meng et al., 2024). Only professional and qualified museum management can significantly help a cultural institution orient itself to its mission and use this mission to benefit marketing strategy and goal achievement in attracting funding from multiple entities, attracting media attention, and capturing new audiences (Szromek, 2022). However, when working as a museum manager, it is essential to realise that this is not work, and the results take time to be apparent. Only through gradual changes and the leader's work tenacity can there be a positive turnaround in the management of a department of cultural tourism (Lukoseviciute et al., 2024).

3. Methodology

The research subjects were the staff of five castles and chateaus, referred to in museum classification as castle museums. The selected objects are situated on the territory of the Slovak Republic, from north to south and east to west, and each is located in a different higher territorial unit (self-governing region). Regarding the interest of domestic and foreign visitors, they are among Slovakia's most attractive cultural stands. When selecting the sample of respondents, we applied quota sampling. The essential prerequisites for participation in the research were the willingness to be interviewed, working in the museum sphere and the anonymity of the respondents. A great asset in selecting the sample was the several years of work experience of one of the authors in the article in the cultural heritage environment, so we could identify precisely which respondents to focus on. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with staff responsible for marketing and communication activities in the castle museums under study. Specifically, these were

cultural-promotional managers, cultural-promotional officers, programme managers, etc., who are marketing decision-makers in their work and are, therefore, referred to as marketing managers in this paper. Respondents were approached individually, through a face-to-face meeting or by telephone. All were interviewed with approximately equal time and a pre-prepared content script. A pyramid model was used to structure the interview, i.e. the questions were divided into introductory, main or specific, and final questions. Additional data were the respondents' identifying features. The primary effort was to elicit responses from the individuals interviewed on the critical areas of the research, namely:

- establishing criteria for segmenting the visiting public,
- targeting communication activities to a specific visitor segment,
- monitoring the effectiveness of marketing communication,
- determining the point of view for evaluating the effectiveness of the funds spent on communication,
- finding out the interest of superiors in the return on resources spent on marketing communication and the way of assigning importance to marketing activities,
- communication management in synergy with the marketing concept,
- monitoring the founder's fulfilment of marketing communication objectives.

The results of the interview were recorded in the form of computer notes. At the same time, for more accurate processing and verification of the information, all five interviews were recorded on a mobile phone using pre-prepared technology. After processing the collected data, the interviews were deleted within 30 days following the privacy policy. While processing the responses, the individual interviews were transcribed and subsequently analysed through descriptive statistics. The resulting data are evaluated verbally, tabulated or graphically.

Research questions

- 1) Is the professional and educational potential of marketing managers sufficient?
- 2) Do these staff members know the typical profile of their visitors, and what segmentation criteria do they apply to them?
- 3) Is marketing communication managed appropriately and correctly?
- 4) Has the desired effect been achieved by monitoring the effectiveness of individual marketing communication tools?
- 5) What management processes are applied by the founders to the marketing communication of monuments?

4. Results

The results of the qualitative research itself reflect the answers to several types of researched problems identified in the environment of monuments during the years 2006 – 2009, 2011 – 2014, 2016 – 2019, and 2021 – 2024 (1st half of the year), as follows. Is the professional and educational potential of marketing managers sufficient? Do they know the typical profile of their visitors, and what segmentation criteria do they apply to them? Is

marketing communication managed appropriately and correctly at all? Has the desired effect been achieved by monitoring the effectiveness of the various marketing communication tools? What management processes are applied by the founders to the marketing communication of heritage sites?

Structure of marketing managers of Castle Museums

The relevant staff plays a vital role in the management processes towards the visitor, i.e., cultural and promotional managers, cultural and promotional officers, and programme managers. The work portfolio of these individuals, referred to as marketing managers, comprises marketing and communication activities through which they try to reach the broadest possible audience. As part of their day-to-day marketing, they decide whether to deploy online or offline tools in the museum practice or whether marketing communications will be integrated. In conjunction with the above activities, the following question can be asked. Can they, in synergy with their educational specialisation and knowledge, implement such decisions so that marketing communication is genuinely effective? That is why, at the beginning of the interview, we wanted to know whether the marketing staff (marketing managers) of the Castle Museums have a degree in marketing or are graduates of a field related to this field. In doing so, we proceeded from the straightforward assumption that adequate education is a fundamental criterion for successful marketing communication management. We were also interested in the age structure, as the global perception is that the staff composition of heritage sites comprises people of retirement age. We also wanted to verify the truth of this statement to find out whether there is still educational potential in the castle museums under study to train, especially younger employees, in marketing and marketing communication. A secondary identifying feature in the employee structure was gender.

The results obtained from the semi-structured interviews can be characterised as follows:

a) gender

The personnel structure of the castle museums has been more or less unchanged over the years, i.e. in all four periods under review in Museum I. – Museum V., there were women in marketing positions. The male representative was dominant only in Museum V. and equally in all four periods. The unattractiveness of museum work for men as breadwinners is primarily due to the low salary. This fact is also confirmed by Tereza Raabová (2011, p. 13), who states: "Women collectively make up $\frac{3}{4}$ of all workers in distinctive, related and non-specific tourism industries. This trend goes hand in hand with low wages in the cultural tourism sector, and the average wage in recreational and cultural activities has long been below the average wage level of the entire economy."

b) age

The age composition of the staff in Table 1 shows that the occupancy of marketing positions in the castle museums is evenly distributed between young people and the middle generation. From the author's experience, most of the marketing managers interviewed

came to work in the museum right after graduating from university and remain in their positions until today. However, the following two facts emerge from the identified results. The castle museums also provide employment opportunities for fresh university employees who need help finding a job in the labour market after graduation. However, the other side shows that a graduate may not be financially valued by heritage sites like an employee with many years of experience.

Table 1: Age composition of marketing staff

Museum type	2006 – 2009	2011 – 2014	2016 – 2019	2021 – 2024
Museum I.	18 – 30 years	31 – 45 years	31 – 45 years	31 – 45 years
Museum II.	46 – 60 years	31 – 45 years	31 – 45 years	31 – 45 years
Museum III.	46 – 60 years	18 – 30 years	18 – 30 years	31 – 45 years
Museum IV.	18 – 30 years	31 – 45 years	31 – 45 years	31 – 45 years
Museum V.	18 – 30 years	18 – 30 years	31 – 45 years	31 – 45 years

Source: own research and processing, 2024

However, let's look at the results presented in Table 1. We conclude that in terms of age, there is considerable potential for further staff training and acquisition of new skills in the Castle Museums surveyed. This statement can be supported by the views of professor and psychologist Marie Vágnerová (2008, p. 9), who emphasises that "an individual in the period of young adulthood (from 20 – 40 years) can cope with certain developmental tasks, professional roles and needs new competencies."

c) Education

The third question yielded a clear answer. Currently (period 2016 – 2019, the same applies for 2021 – 2024), the employees of the monuments surveyed have a university degree. However, if we were to examine whether this was the situation in previous periods in the castle museums, the answer would be no. Between 2006 and 2009, women with secondary education worked in marketing positions at Museum II. and Museum III. Since 2010, there has been a change in staff in Museum II. and Museum III., where the female staff member has completed her higher education, first at her bachelor's and then at the master's level of her university studies.

d) Educational qualifications

The fourth question confirmed the expectations of the authors of the article that the education of the respondents would be of a social or humanistic orientation, mainly linked to the history curriculum. The latter is more suitable for curators or curators of collections. A positive finding was the results of the educational potential in Museum I. – Museum III. in the years 2011 – 2014 and 2016 – 2019, 2021 – 2024. The study programmes mentioned above are at least partly related to marketing and communication skills, as the study programmes mentioned above have the subjects of marketing, management, economics, etc., at the core of their education.

Table 2: Educational specialisation of marketing staff

Museum type	2006 – 2009	2011 – 2014	2016 – 2019	2021 – 2024
Museum I.	Pedagogy	International business	International business	International business
Museum II.	Economics	Project management	Project management	Project management
Museum III.	Economics	Museology	Public administration	Public administration
Museum IV.	Social work	History	History	History
Museum V.	History	History	History	History

Source: own research and processing, 2024

At the same time, however, the results of this question pointed to a long-standing problem of monuments in the performance of marketing communication activities, namely, that the education of marketing managers of castle museums needs to correspond to their job titles to a large extent. This may lead to unsystematically implementing marketing or communication activities towards visitors.

A managerial view of the visitor to the castle museums

Any museum that wants to succeed in the leisure market should know the profile of its visitors. This is extremely important when designing programmes so the museum knows to which target group the product will be directed. An exhibition or cultural and social event that does not have a clearly defined target audience - the group it wants to reach - has little chance of success. In the same way, this information is vital in targeting communication activities that lead to maintaining or increasing attendance. For this reason, in our interviews with marketing managers, we were interested in knowing whether they know the typical profile of their visitors and what criteria they use to segment the visiting public.

a) *typical visitor profile of castle museums*

Four respondents answered in the affirmative when asked whether the castle museums know about their visitors' typical profile. Museum IV. expressed a negative opinion, as they did not conduct a detailed analysis of visitor numbers. We note that the identification of the typical visitor profile receives almost sufficient attention in Museum I. since, during all the periods studied, it had information on the profile composition of its visitors, which it segments according to demographic, geographic and socio-economic criteria. In three of the four periods (2011 – 2014, 2016 – 2019, 2021 – 2024), Museum II. was able, in most cases, to indicate the typical identifying features of its audience and, in addition to this information, it had set precise criteria to demographically and geographically segment the visiting public. On her initiative, the Marketing Manager of Museum III. strives to identify the typical profile of the visiting public and, through demographic and geographical segmentation, seeks to develop specialised programs and provide other complementary services. In recent years, Museum Manager V. has been working to identify the audience that visits the National Historic Site and targeting museum products and

communication activities through demographic and behavioural segmentation. As a history graduate, he admits that he needs to gain some marketing skills, e.g., expertise in implementing social media campaigns, in which the museum has significant and untapped reserves.

b) visitor segmentation criteria

As with the previous question, and to identify the issue about segmentation criteria, Museum IV. stated that it does not implement them and has no plans to implement them shortly. Other museums select the visiting public according to several aspects of their activities, but the standard features were demographic and geographical segmentation.

Picture 2: Segmentation criteria of Museums I., II., III., V.

Source: own research and processing, 2024

We consider the so-called partial segmentation criteria mentioned above insufficient.

c) targeting marketing and communication activities to age groups

The data clearly showed that while heritage sites use marketing and communication campaigns targeting the precise age groups of the visiting public, in some museums, the targeting has been constant over the years, as documented in Table 3. Moreover, castle museums forget entirely the critical fact that not all museum products, due to their specificity, can be communicated to a broad audience. A typical example is exhibitions more suitable for art lovers than families with children. The same is true, e.g. children's holiday shows, which will have a communicative and effective visitor impact if explicitly

highlighted as family-friendly products within the communication infrastructure and communication flows.

Table 3: Age group targeting of museums

Museum type	2006 – 2009	2011 – 2014	2016 – 2019	2021 – 2024
Museum I.	35 – 45 year-old people	35 – 45 year-old people	35 – 45 year-old people	35 – 45 year-old people
Museum II.	20 – 40-year-old people	families with children	families with children	families with children
Museum III.	all groups	18 – 55 year-old people	18 – 55 year-old people	18 – 55 year-old people
Museum IV.	pupils, students, teachers	pupils, students, teachers	pupils, students, teachers	pupils, students, teachers
Museum V.	all groups	25 – 60 year-old people	25 – 60 year-old people	25 – 60 year-old people

Source: own research and processing, 2024

The summarised responses in Table 3 yielded one very noteworthy finding. In their marketing activities and communication campaigns, the Castle Museums are utterly oblivious to several specific segments of the public that may significantly impact increasing future visitation to heritage sites, namely, the child visitor, the 50+ generation, the female generation, and cultural consumers with disabilities.

Management of marketing communication management processes

In this part, we deal with the issues related to the management of marketing communication of the castle museums as a whole, including its supporting processes, i.e. we specifically investigate:

- How do they define the effectiveness of marketing communication, and do they pay any attention to its evaluation concerning the return on funds invested in communication?
- From what point of view do monuments evaluate the effectiveness of the funds spent on communication, and how are their directors (castellans) interested in the return on the funds spent on marketing communication?
- How do the directors (castellans) of the castle museums approach marketing activities, and do they consider them a priority?
- Have the founders of individual castle museums developed a concept for managing individual marketing and communication activities?
- How does the founder of the castle museums intervene (guide) in marketing and communication activities, and do the founders require the monuments to set marketing communication objectives and meet them?
- Does the founder of monuments apply the 3E principle (economy, efficiency, effectiveness) when controlling marketing communication?

This section's results address both closed and open questions. Since the data identified in all four periods yield similar findings, their treatment will be textual.

a) *monitoring the effectiveness of marketing communications*

In conjunction with the communication infrastructure of the castle museums and the objectives of marketing communication, we investigated how marketing managers approach the measurement of the effectiveness of marketing communication (efficiency), according to what criteria they evaluate the effectiveness of the funds spent on communication, and whether the directors (castellans) of the individual monuments are interested in the indicators of economy. At the same time, we wanted to know what emphasis the management of castles and chateaux places on marketing activities in the museum's activities and whether they consider them a priority.

Since most of the questions in this issue circle were open-ended, marketing managers needed to be more apprehensive about answering these questions at each period of the research. The reason for this was that measuring the effectiveness of marketing communications as a supporting process for marketing communications management, in particular, has had significant shortcomings for several years in a row, and this unfavourable state of affairs needs to be improved. An important problem is that castles need to track the effectiveness of the individual components of marketing communications for the period 2006 – 2024. The reasons for this are as follows:

- The marketing managers interviewed need to explain the meaning of this phrase adequately. They consider the increase in the number of visitors to be a clear benefit of the effectiveness of marketing communication. Thanks to these answers, it can be concluded that the insufficient marketing education of these employees causes an absence of knowledge, which is then reflected in their job performance.
- The neglect of monitoring this indicator and the need for more information about marketing communication effectiveness is caused to a lesser extent by ignorance of measuring communication activities. However, the main reason for this is that most marketing managers need more time in their work activities to measure the effectiveness of marketing communication. From the author's experience, the failure to track the return on resources spent on marketing communication is not due to improper coordination of working time. The reality is that there is a need for more interest from directors (castellans) of castle museums in such results. The marketing managers themselves eventually confirmed this fact in interviews. The directors of all museums, even those founded by a private owner, explicitly consider visitor statistics to be the optimal way of evaluating performance indicators and do not attach importance to other numerical statements.

Summarising the facts identified above, we conclude that monitoring the effectiveness of marketing communications has stayed the same from 2006 to 2024, more than eighteen years later. The very unfavourable state of the evaluation of the effectiveness of communication activities is caused not only by the absence of marketing knowledge of the staff but also by the explicitly indifferent attitude of the directors of the monuments to

this activity. Marketing managers can dispose of the funds earmarked for communication without control or feedback. The resigned management of castle museums is directly related to the advanced age of the castellans.

The management of the three castle museums out of the five surveyed monuments has the status of pensioners, which results in uninnovative management and a rigid attitude towards marketing as a whole. This is evidenced by the answer to the question: "Does the museum director consider marketing activities to be a priority in the museum's activities?" As many as three out of five marketing managers answered that the management of castles and chateaux is not inclined towards marketing activities and needs to identify with the marketing concept, which is said to give a commercial character to a heritage object. This directly relates to the effectiveness of marketing communication and also acts as a barrier for the staff responsible for marketing. Even if marketing managers were to initiate more effective management of performance indicators of their own volition, they would not find their supervisor sympathetic to such an action.

b) management of marketing communication processes

In the questions from the final third of the interview, we were interested in coordinating the marketing communication process in the environment of monuments. For example, we checked more closely whether the management of marketing communication of the castle museums is in line with the founder's marketing concept or communication strategy. We also wanted to know whether the founder requires the examined cultural tourism departments not only to set but also to meet the objectives for marketing communication and whether the 3E principle is used in controlling marketing communication management.

Evaluating the marketing managers' responses was very straightforward because one type of so-called short universal response, the word no, was cyclically repeated during the four time periods studied. In other words, in none of the castle museums does the founder have a marketing concept through which the marketing activities of the monuments are managed. Surprisingly, a negative answer was also given during 2006 – 2024 at Museum V., a heritage building whose founder is a private owner. The negative answer was repeated five times in the other three questions, i.e. all castle museums do not have marketing communication objectives set for the founder, the founder does not require the heritage objects to meet the goals for marketing communication, and the founder does not apply the 3E principle when controlling the management of marketing communication. We note that the marketing communication management process needs more systematic, with objectives and strategy. The approval of the visuals of the marketing campaigns in Museum V. by the founder is a kind of salvation. Since the object is in private hands, such an activity is logical. Still, with other management processes of marketing communication, it can be considered only a peripheral matter.

We unequivocally state that the founders' approach to the communication presentation of monuments needs to be more systematic. For several years, there has been a lack of any developed strategy and concept that would translate into an orderly

management of the communication infrastructure of monuments, the presentation of museum products through the mutual integrity of communication tools, focusing on specific target groups and the development of brand awareness of individual castles and chateaux. The absence of such a valuable document for practice is reflected in the neglect of monitoring indicators of the economy, efficiency and effectiveness of marketing communication (3E principle). The four public sector managers of the castle museums need help understanding the significant potential of marketing communication to increase visitor numbers and develop cultural heritage, and also to be completely unaware that they are also making decisions about public finances when managing communication processes. The very approach of the last founder is also incomprehensible as it invests its funds in this activity. It should be noted, however, that the operation and public accessibility of a listed building is only a marginal matter of business for its owner, a private owner.

5. Discussion

The application of the right marketing concept to maintain and increase the number of visitors to individual castle museums is to some extent influenced by the regulations of their founder, but above all by the management of each monument. For the management of these institutions, it is not the satisfied visitor that is the priority at the moment, but the income from admission fees. This extreme is one of the reasons why marketing practices are more challenging to enforce in individual castle museums. It is almost inconceivable that commercial companies of the same size as individual heritage sites would need a clearly defined concept by which they want to establish themselves on the market. This fact has been a perennial and fundamental marketing problem for Slovak museums for several years. It is truly astonishing, even incomprehensible that only a few founders should be bothered by the fact that its organisational unit has yet to have a marketing concept in the 21st century. This is all the more so when one castle museum is under the jurisdiction of a private owner. Indeed, with a decent concept, it is possible to create integrity in communication, which should cut across the whole spectrum of marketing activities and act as a driver for audience development.

Therefore, managing every monument should be to redefine the institution's mission and urgently create a marketing concept. It must set out the priorities and objectives on which each of the museum's departments will base their activities and towards which their activities will be directed. Within the framework of setting up a marketing concept, it is necessary to integrate all marketing activities into one place so that everything is evident in the marketing activities of the castle museums. Therefore, within the managerial function of organising, the museum management should organise and structure the work so that the marketing department carries out and is responsible for the marketing activities.

Currently, individual monuments have presentation and marketing departments in their organisational structure, but some marketing procedures are carried out by directors or curators, curators, collections documenters, etc. Organising marketing and assigning marketing responsibilities to one unit does not mean that the creative activity of other professional staff will no longer be necessary. Not at all; the creative thinking and ideas of

curators, documenters, and museum educators can significantly benefit the castle or chateau itself. The marketing department should consult with these or other museum staff, including practitioners, when setting marketing goals, tactics for increasing attendance and reaching cultural audiences, determining the communication mix and dynamics, financial options for implementing the concept, and other key marketing activities. Subsequently, the marketing concept will be presented to the management of the heritage object. The management of the castle or chateau, in cooperation with the founder, should assess the systemic nature of the individual steps with an estimate of future developments, the main tasks and priorities of the concept, compliance with museum legislation, the timetable, socio-economic factors, the effectiveness of the objectives set and their impact on museum activities.

When creating a marketing concept, we recommend that castle museums consider the four aspects that determine it: collections and the monument's mission, visitor satisfaction, public benefit and quality as a goal, and exogenous factors.

Picture 3: Proposal for the marketing concept of the castle museum

Source: own processing, 2024; theoretical background: Paniagua et al., 2022; Kincl, 2004

In terms of the implementation of the concept, the castle museums should take care of the balanced position of the collections and visitors, i.e. not to focus dominantly either on the collections or on the visitors, but to bring them as close as possible to each other with the help of marketing and marketing communication. The approach of equal proportionality, visitor versus collections, is very successful in the environment of the most famous foreign museums and is often applied in practice. The success of the implementation of the concept is also influenced by the quality of the services provided, which should also be one of the objectives of the heritage object.

Only by providing quality services will the Castle Museums fulfil their mission, i.e. the marketing concept must reflect the social mission. The fourth component, exogenous

factors, has a powerful influence on castles. These are beyond the immediate control of the museum; it is the so-called battle for control of the castle and castle museum. In practice, these are the interests of the founder or owner of the monument, including their financial possibilities and potential. These factors can be called the other P of the marketing mix – problem-solving.

If we look at the marketing concept as a tool for managing the marketing activities of castle museums, a detailed marketing concept based on the environment of the castles and chateaux can increase visitors to these monuments. Implementing the marketing approach must become a synergistic part of all the practices of the heritage objects, a tool for realising the mission and objectives of the presentation of the collections of these institutions, taking into account the needs of the public. It will certainly not be a matter of one year, but a demanding long-term process requiring an understanding of the principles and principles of marketing by all the management staff and the staff of the heritage objects. If the castle museums want to become a modern part of society and not just a place where museum collections are stored, marketing and communication with the public must be more than just peripheral issues. They must be activities that are reflected in the entire functioning of the organisation, with appropriate financial and personnel support.

Managing museums' marketing processes should involve acquiring, comparing, and assessing data on the suitability of deploying individual marketing communication tools, i.e., measuring their effectiveness. In practice, this would evaluate fulfilling the set communication and marketing objectives. Such objectives in the castle museums might not only be to influence visitor numbers in conjunction with admission fee revenues but also to maintain the reputation and brand awareness, to inform about the institution's intentions and mission, to build a positive image, to popularise specific museum areas in a non-traditional way, to deepen relations with the internal public or to address particular visitor segments, e.g. professional audiences, etc.

Monitoring the effectiveness of marketing communication should be a significant activity for the castle museums in the management processes of marketing communication. Evaluation indicators would not only allow to compare the expected and achieved level in the categories that were the content of the communication plan, but through the evaluation, the heritage objects would be able to gain insight into the correctness of the decisions on the appropriateness of the deployment of individual marketing communication tools. At the same time, the results would serve as a basis for implementing further campaigns in terms of the dynamics of the communication infrastructure.

6. Conclusion

If we look globally at the arts and culture sector, which includes the castle museums, we conclude that these areas generate a wide range of opportunities. Be it creating new job opportunities, increasing the attractiveness of the area, influencing the tax revenues of the city or region, or attracting new investments (Walter, 2015). To make their benefit effect more effective, it is necessary not only to apply the elements of marketing management to

the cultural sphere but also to follow the current marketing trends. For the museum sector, this creates a space for sustaining cultural production, raising awareness, and stimulating demand to visit the cathedrals of cultural tourism.

The application of modern management principles in museum practice is also related to the adoption of marketing management, which is nowadays a necessity (Leal & Silva, 2024). Museum owners or founders should also realise its importance. Therefore, it is also indispensable to incorporate a marketing approach into the museum management processes. In conclusion, considering cultural consumers' needs and disseminating cultural values, castle museums, management, and marketing are interrelated elements. It is therefore necessary to find a mutual harmony between them, balance all the museum functions equally, and make it function as efficiently as possible.

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